

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF JOB SATISFACTION ON THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN EMPLOYEES' PARTICIPATION AND JOB PERFORMANCE: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM JORDANIAN CONTEXT

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the mediating influence of job satisfaction on the relationship between employee's participation and job performance in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department. This study also employed questionnaires to gather data from the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department employees. Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) was used to determine whether a relationship exists between the mediator, independent, and dependent variables. From the questionnaires administered, 310 were valid for analysis. The results revealed that employee participation and job performance have a significant positive relationship. This study's findings revealed that employee's participation significantly increase the job satisfaction of an individual. The result indicated that job satisfaction partially mediated the relationship between employee's participation and job performance in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department. Therefore, this study suggested that all managers who are intended and assigned to increase the performance of overall industries can achieve their goals and objectives through job satisfaction by focusing on decision-making participation (DMP). Besides, to build the quality of the trade relationship where organizations can acquaint DMP with increment job performance, the view of authoritative help for their employees' prosperity can yield and prompt more positive performance by employees.

Keywords: Employees Participation; Job Satisfaction, Job Performance, PLS-SEM.

1. INTRODUCTION

Society and organisations engage with each other to meet human needs, either to earn money by creating and selling goods and services or to receive compensation for the services they provide. In doing so, it allows organisations to pool all of its resources including efficient use of human expertise to fulfill the fundamental economic rule. This partnership is gradually gaining intensity. What employees and employers expect from each other may vary and cause friction, and if treated poorly, the company's predefined goals will not be achieved. To ensure that both employer and employee agree with their aspirations, humanization of the workplace appears to be highly important. Orally or verbally, workers are well briefed about what they are expected to do. Organisations are uncertain of how much hard work will be done in meeting

duties or how much positive work will be carried out when remaining with the organisation. Furthermore, there is still a need for companies to consider certain returns on investments in the humanization of the workplace (Alkhwaldi et al., 2022; Al-Okaily et al., 2022 a,b; Groen, et al., 2017). In today's rapidly changing environment, effectively managing employee performance has become not only the norm but the sine qua non, particularly in the public sector (Ehiane, Adejuwon, & Goyayi, 2019). However, it has become difficult to do so, with organisational pressures accumulating barriers, excessive bureaucracy, and low levels of morality and satisfaction exacerbating frustration and bad morality, leading to poor results (Jacobsen & Andersen, 2015). It has been argued that resolving these issues requires leaders who can thoroughly understand them and who have the right style of leadership (Liu et al., 2013; Ohemeng, Amoako, & Darko, 2018). Job success has drawn the attention of many scholars and practitioners (Ahmad et al., 2016, 2015).

However, employees have become the organisation's key assets in today's work environment (David 2011), and recognition of the importance of their role in achieving the goals of the organisations has increased dramatically (Zhu et al. 2015). As a result, the debate among academics, practitioners and policymakers on the involvement of employees in the decision-making process and the shift toward decreasing centralization in decision-making has attracted the interest of many stakeholders (Shaed et al. 2015). Among these, many considered moving from the traditional way of dealing with employees by putting orders to the reconstruction of the company based on the decentralization of the decision-making process, allowing workers the opportunity to engage in this process and the trust between managers and their employees as significant ingredients for the survival of the organisation (Stohl and Cheney).

Several studies have reported that employees' participation in decision-making (EPDM) exerts a positive influence on employees outcomes and behavior in organizations. EPDM motivates employees to show a desirable behavior (Coch and French Jr 1948, Vroom 1964), encourages them to show their talents through participation, and increase their feeling to be connected to organizational goals (Heller et al. 1998). Han et al. (2010) determined that EPDM has a positive relationship with their feeling of psychological ownership, which makes them feel like they are the owners of the organization, and they are ready to spend more time and more prepared to assume more to enhance organization performance. Furthermore, many researchers found a positive effect, even though in some cases the effect was minimal, of EPDM on job satisfaction (Locke and Schweiger 1979, Wagner Iii et al. 1997, Cox et al. 2006, Karatepe and Olugbade 2009, Zhu et al. 2015, Bakan et al. 2004), and productivity (Matteson and Ivancevich 1999, Miller and Monge 1986b, Chizoba et al. 2019, Abdulai and Shafiwu 2014), motivation (Bhuiyan 2010, Bhatti and Qureshi 2007, Bakan et al. 2004, Chizoba et al. 2019), and morals and commitment (Abdulai and Shafiwu 2014, Akuoko et al. 2012). In contrast, many studies revealed that employees' satisfaction could be improved significantly when they are involved more in the decision-making process (Bhatti and Qureshi 2007, Tourani and Rast 2012, Alas 2007, Holland et al. 2011, Advani and Gulzar 2018, García Gustavo 2019). As a result, their performance can be achieved as it is affected by their satisfaction (Uzun and Ozdem 2017, Afshar and Doosti 2016, Ölçer and Florescu 2015, Khan et al. 2019, Vandenabeele 2009).

However, Jordan is a developing country that experiences a fast-growing economy from 2000 to 2009, with a growth in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to be estimated as 6.5%. However, since 2010, the growth of GDP has declined to approximately 2.5% (The Economic Policy Council 2017). As Jordan suffers from the conflicts in the Middle East region and from the scarcity of its resources, Jordan tried to create an internal fundi g resource by giving the opportunity to its taxation system (Al-Okaily, 2021; Al-Okaily et al., 2020; Malkawi and Haloush 2008). Taxation has several disadvantages which encompass lack of transparency, corruption, inefficiency, and the high burden on the taxpayers. However, in developing countries, taxation is a significant financial resource for governments, especially in developing countries (Al-Bashayreh et al., 2022; Al-Adwan et al., 2022; Al-Qudah et al., 2022; Al-Okaily et al., 2021 a,b). Using taxes, governments possess a constant fund for their expenditures, services, and projects, and are able to achieve different goals on many levels. For instance, on the social level, taxes are very helpful when it comes to distributing the income and resources in the society. Higher taxes can be used to reduce the demand of undesired products like cigarettes and alcohols. In addition, taxation is very useful to protect national products in competing for the external ones in the local market (Al-Naimat 2013). Taxation in Jordan is a responsibility of the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax department (ISTD), which was among the first Arabic governmental departments to be certified with quality management system (QMS) ISO 9001 in 2005, and plays a significant role in providing funding to the national economy of Jordan (ISTD 2017). Therefore, there is a necessity to investigate the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between employees' participation in decision-making process (EPDM) on employees' job performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mahoney (1963) proposed job performance in Listiyaningsih (2005) as the performance of individual members of the company in managerial activities that involve preparation, investigation, management, training, monitoring, and initiating negotiations with external parties and representations. According to Milani (1975), the degree of managers' involvement and influence in the budgeting process is a condition which distinguishes between participatory and non-participatory budgets. An organisation has processes and procedures related to the budget planning process and its use which may be different from other organisations. Eker (2007) reported a connection between spending support and administrative execution is positive and significant. Studies have indicated that worker commitment has a positive relationship with a representative's effectiveness, joy and profitability (Pfeffer, 1994; Wagner, 1994; Verma, 1995; Wang and Lim, 2008). Studies have also demonstrated that representative commitment has a positive connection with a worker's effectiveness, bliss and efficiency (Pfeffer, 1994; Wagner, 1994; Verma, 1995). DMP's most prominent advantage is that it controls certain parts of workgroup decent variety (Friday-Stroud and Sutterfield, 2007; Ingleby, 2011; ScottLadd et al., 2006; Wadesango, 2012; Chirenje et al., 2013). It has been accentuated that the assortment of tasks and occupation exercises empower laborers to participate in a dynamic cycle. Lastly, DMP has significant constructive outcomes on work fulfillment. The literature on the contribution of DMP in hierarchical achievement shows

several negative connections. Investigations by Kees Looise et al. (2011), Gartner (2008) Adesango (2010), Bhatti et al. (2011), Hughes et al. (2015), Peter and Amrik (2016) on non-association commitment at the hierarchical level, including both immediate and circuitous commitment, reported that worker contribution in dynamic was a specific subject in mechanical relations which do not translate to hierarchical needs. We hypothesize on certain rationales:

2.1 Employees Participation and Job Satisfaction

Lee (2009) notes that budget has a significant effect on human behaviour, especially for people who are directly involved in writing or developing budgets. Job efficiency, job satisfaction, subordinates' attitudes, supervisors and moral attitudes can be realised through someone's participation towards something of value, both for the part he is engaged in on a daily basis and for the organization (Alzoubi et al., 2022 a,b; Allozi et al., 2022; Alshurideh, 2014). Lee (2009) mentioned that managers' engagement in budgeting would improve productivity and develop high-level project managers. High employee productivity is explained as someone with job satisfaction on their supervisor and colleagues. Lee (2009) found that participation has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Employees participation will lead to greater confidence in the proper performance of their duties, which will then have a better impact on the work. Christopher et al. (2006) commented that JS is a situation-sensitive work feeling that is often great (satisfied), and some incidents can worsen it (unsatisfied). Michael (2006) and Foster et al. (2010) stressed "Morale is also characterised as equal to JS." Some workers may be more satisfied with their employment, while others may be less satisfied as Ivancevich and Hoon (2002) recorded that "job satisfaction levels may vary depending on sector, country, and type of employee." Pay is usually compensated for the sacrifices made by workers to attain goals and make their work excellent and the value generated by their workers. John Purcell (2004) emphasised that money is not the prime motivator in jobs for most workers. Tangible benefits actually rank fourth, behind enjoyable JS work and a sense of accomplishment. O'Leary et al. (2009), Kang et al. (2015), Alhouti et al. (2016) and Boddy (2016) reveal that male employees display a higher degree of JS (overall) than female employees, while female employees were found to be more comfortable with customer relationships than their counterparts on the other side of JS. Thus, this study proposes:

2.2 Job Satisfaction and Job performance

Puspaningsih (2002) claims that if employees feel the justice and extrinsic rewards (salary and promotion) and intrinsic rewards (feeling what has been achieved), employees performance will increase. This condition will lead to a higher degree of satisfaction. If managers are happy with the work they have done because the manager already includes the budget involvement, it will positively affect employees performance in which the budget's aim has been achieved. Techniques of reward, which explicitly relate the compensation of the agent to individual results, are expected to result in improved efficiency (Lazear, 1999; Baker et al., 1988). Productivity is rarely a goal, but not an accomplishment according to Brayfield and Crockett (1955). Vroom's very comprehensive literature (1964) failed to endorse and suggest a close relationship between JS and employees productivity. As per performance theory (Campbell, 1990), performance refer to acts of behavioural people which have an effect on the goals of the

organisation. This can be positive or negative, and the action can be treated either as part of the job or outside of the duties prescribed. Kalyta (2009) and ASSOCHAM (2016) argued that components of compensation play an important part in EP. There are a number of researches that suggest that rewards can be related to different organisational goals at various management levels. The overall organisational preparation and implementation of plans is more concerning, whereas the benefits from lower-level workers should be closely connected to their roles (Horngren et al., 2000 and Nazir and Islam, 2017). Global culture has a profound effect on the level of employee JS, and multinational companies in particular must track JS and performance reviews in the local cultural context (Eskildsen et al., 2010). According to Schulman (2007), "a number of practitioners and researchers discovered that the JS amount explicitly or indirectly hits the output of employees". As the satisfaction level goes down, the performance deteriorates and an improvement in the level of JS increases the results (Alwan and Alshurideh, 2022; Alzoubi et al., 2020; Hayajneh et al., 2021). Thus, it is essential to understand the factors that influence work satisfaction in order job satisfaction. Thus, this study propose:

2.3 The mediating influence of Job Satisfaction on the relationship between Employees Participation in Decision-Making Process (EPDM) and Job Performance

Theory of organisational support (OST) indicates that workers develop a subjective understanding of the degree to which the company values their efforts and cares about their well-being. Shanock and Eisenberger (2006) established a clear positive relationship between the perception of supervisors / immediate bosses about organisational support and the perception of their subordinates about organisational support. If supervisors are positive about organisational support, subordinates will demonstrate positive reactions and vice versa. Employers' inducements are found to be positively correlated with POS according to the perception of employees and are negatively correlated with the perception of employers' obligations as stated by Coyle et al. (2005). A meta-analysis by renowned scholar and principle creators (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Bednall et al., 2014) further highlighted three major POS antecedents which are compensation and working conditions, assistance from supervisor / immediate boss, and procedural judges. Perceived Organizational Support by Hekman et al. (2009) has had the most positive impact on the job performance of employees when workers are strongly associated with the organisation and weakly associated with the career. There is a clear sense in the literature that perceived organisation is a variable that affects almost all employee behaviour model in every organisational setting (Aburayya et al., 2020; Kurdi et al., 2020; Ammari et al., 2017). Therefore, we propose:

3. METHODOLOGY

A quantitative method was used in this descriptive study. The population of this study was 1542 employees. As this study aims to assess EPDM and job performance in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department through quantifying the perceptions of the employees in this department, the population of this study included all the employees in the department. According to the annual report of ISTD in 2017, which is the most recent annual report, the number of employees in ISTD was 1556 employee. among those, there are 14 employees who

occupy higher levels of management in the department, and 1542 employees from the first, the second, and the third grade (ISTD 2017). The sample size of this study was 310 employees from the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). The technique used for sampling was simple random sampling. Neuman (2014) proposed that a researcher should create a detailed section framework to carry out simple random sampling by selecting functions from the frame and employing a mathematical selection method, and then trace the exact item selected in the sample.

3.1 Data Collection Technique

The study was carried out in Jordan, and the results were obtained using self-administered questionnaire, where respondents were asked to complete the survey themselves. The goal of this study was to reduce costs with the elimination of the respondent of devices and things, including computer software (Willett, 2017). The adapted questionnaire combined and adapted various research instruments from related previous studies. The questionnaire was adapted to provide a clear understanding of the phenomenon and constructs of this research study in Jordan.

3.2 Data Analysis Technique

Partial Least Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was used in this analysis to evaluate the data obtained (Aws et al., 2021; Al-Okaily & Al-Okaily, 2022). Before conducting the actual data analysis, the researcher performed a data mining procedure to ensure adequate representation of the data. In addition, the data collected were analyzed using SmartPLS 3.0 to check the fitness of the research's proposed model or structure and to evaluate the proposed research hypotheses. PLS-SEM was also used to examine the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between employees' participation in the decision-making process (EPDM) on job performance. There are some rationales for using PLS-SEM. The aim of this analysis was to examine the previously defined causal relations between constructs. However, PLS-SEM was the tool used by this study to evaluate the data obtained from the respondents. In light of the empirical knowledge and subjective causal assumptions, PLS-SEM is a quantitative method to check and analyze certain causal relations. SEM is a corroborative approach that is used to evaluate if the model generated for the study is knowledge valid. SEM is a combination of study of the component and specific degenerations. SEM can be individualized into two parts. The estimation model is the part which relates inactive factors to calculated factors. The basic model is the part where inactive factors are associated.

4. RESULTS

A total of 310 valid responses were collected from the questionnaire administered. The results presented were based on the purpose of the study which used the research results of the PLS-SEM. In ensuring that the data were free from missing values, this study conducted frequency and missing value analysis for each measuring item. The results of the data screening showed that there was a minimum amount of missing data which was replaced by using the

median variable responses for each measuring item. Outliers suggest an unnormal value for observations on a single variable (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). For unit-variate reporting, in addition to analysing histograms and box-plots, the standardised (z) value for each value was assessed (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Continuing with Hair et al., (2016), the regular score of an outlier should be ± 4.0 or higher. Thus, any Z-score higher than 4 or below -4 is perceived as an outlier.

4.1 Multicollinearity, and Data Normality Assessment

Focusing on the measuring model, as postulated by Awang (2014), the study analysed the normality of the remaining items following the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess the distribution for each item or variable associated in the measurement model.

Table 2 demonstrates that for all products used in the measurement model, the skewness and kurtosis values were lower than -2.0 and 4.0, respectively, suggesting that the data were normally distributed as prescribed by the statistics law. It implies that the data attained the standard limit of a multivariate normality distribution.

Thus, the study is proceeding for further analysis. In this study, the problem of collinearity for the structural model was evaluated by applying VIF. The VIF values should be less than 5.

Therefore, Table demonstrates that there was no problem of collinearity among the items in the structural model.

Table 2: Multicollinearity and Data Normality Assessment

	Skewness	Kurtosis	Tolerance	VIF
JOB PERFORMANCE	-0.683	-0.005		
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION	-0.267	-0.725	0.559	1.79
JOB SATISFACTION	-0.668	0.386	0.541	1.43

4.2 Reliability and Validity

The reliability was measured by evaluating the composite reliability values using the internal consistency method. All variables indicated reliability for composites (values greater than 0.7) (Wong, 2010) as shown in Table 4. Wherever the reliability of the indicators (squaring of outer loadings) is found to be less than 0.7 but composite reliability and AVE is appropriate for the measure, then the indicators were preserved as they indicate clarification (Becker, 2017).

Convergent validity was evaluated by measuring AVE (explained average variance) values that surpass 0.5 (Table 3), while discriminant validity was evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker test (Table 4). The conditions for discriminant validity are that for each latent variable, the square root of AVE should be higher than the correlation between latent variables. The variables follow the requirements for discriminant validity as presented in Table 5.

Table 3: Loading and Internal Consistency Reliability of the Measurement Model

Variables	Loading	CR	AVE	CA
JOB PERFORMANCE		0.939	0.687	0.923
JP1	0.721			
JP2	0.817			
JP3	0.858			
JP4	0.851			
JP5	0.838			
JP6	0.832			
JP7	0.876			
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION		0.957	0.584	0.952
EP1	Deleted			
EP2	Deleted			
EP3	Deleted			
EP4	0.655			
EP5	0.72			
EP6	0.774			
EP7	0.783			
EP8	0.783			
EP9	0.736			
EP10	0.779			
EP11	0.748			
EP12	0.808			
EP13	0.773			
EP14	0.768			
EP15	0.813			
EP16	0.765			
EP17	0.802			
EP18	0.719			
EP19	0.786			
EP20	Deleted			
Job Satisfaction		0.931	0.552	0.918
JS1	0.640			
JS2	0.784			
JS3	0.802			
JS4	0.744			
JS5	Deleted			
JS6	Deleted			
JS7	0.763			
JS8	0.767			
JS9	0.812			
JS10	0.809			
JS11	0.73			
JS12	0.691			
JS13	Deleted			
JS14	0.602			

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker criterion analysis to check discriminant validity

	Employees Participation	Job Performance	Job Satisfaction
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION	0.764		
JOB PERFORMANCE	0.745	0.829	
JOB SATISFACTION	0.67	0.643	0.743

4.3 The Results of the Structural Model Analysis

The first step of Smart PLS is to specify the research framework or model in a schematic diagram based on the theory. Additionally, the analysis system was translated into graphic SmartPLS 3.0. The diagram, which starts with employee’s participation, job satisfaction, and job performance, is illustrated in Figure 1. The arrows connecting this study's constructs were determined by the hypotheses. The single-headed arrows were used to check the study construct's causal effect. In addition, the standardized estimate for this study's structural model, showing the factor loading for each item and mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between employees’ participation in decision-making process (EPDM) on the job performance, was described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Smart PLS Standardized Result

Table 5: Summary of Path Coefficients

	PATH COEFFICIENTS	STDEV	P-VALUES	Q ²	F ²	DECISION
JOB PERFORMANCE				0.027	0.073	
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION -> JOB PERFORMANCE	0.650	0.066	0.000			Supported
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION -> JOB SATISFACTION	0.669	0.04	0.000			Supported
JOB SATISFACTION -> JOB PERFORMANCE	0.208	0.07	0.003			Supported

The summed influences of the study's SmartPLS were presented in Table 5. It shows the path coefficients, standard deviation (STDEV), and the probability value (P-value) according to the results of the study's respective construct. Employee participation and job performance also revealed a significant positive relationship. The results showed that a 1 percent increase in employee participation will result in a 0.650 increase in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department's job performance. The result in Table 5 showed a positive and statistically significant relationship between employee participation and job satisfaction. The path coefficient in the employee participation and job satisfaction relationship indicated that an increase of 1 percent in employee participation would result in an increase of 0.669 in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department job satisfaction. However, the results reported that job satisfaction's exerted a significant positive effect on job performance. However, the predictive relevance Q² of the exogenous latent constructions was above zero in the present study (Hair et al., 2014). Moreover, the exogenous latent constructs f² was considered a minor effect (Henseler & Chin 2010). The R² value indicates the extent to which the independent variables explained independent variables for the variance. The R² estimates for the model were shown in Table 6. It showed the magnitude of variance on the dependent variable which the independent variables represent. Table 6 presented that job performance's predictors explain 64.7 per cent of its variance. In other words, the job performance error variance is about 35.3 percent of the Job Performance difference itself. Table 6 also estimated that job satisfaction's predictors explain 44.8 percent of its variance, thus, the error variance of job satisfaction is approximately 55.2 percent of the variance of job satisfaction itself.

Table 6: Summary of the R²

	R ²	R ² Adjusted
JOB PERFORMANCE	0.647	0.639
JOB SATISFACTION	0.448	0.447

4.6 Testing the Job Satisfaction as a mediator in the Relationship between Employees Participation and Job Performance

To examine the mediating effect of job satisfaction, the researcher assessed the importance of the direct effect without integrating the mediator variable (Job Satisfaction) into the PLS 3 direction model. The table showed the meaning of the coefficients of indirect effect and total

effect path from performing the bootstrapping procedure (with 310 tests, 5000 subsamples and no sign changes). Thus, Table 7 showed that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between employee participation on job performance in the Jordanian Department of Income and Sales Tax.

Table 7: Mediation Influence of Job Satisfaction on Relationship between Employees Participation and job performance

Construct		Beta	p	Result
DIRECT EFFECT	Employees Participation -> Job Performance	0.650	0.000	Sig
MEDIATION MODEL				
INDIRECT EFFECT	Employees Participation -> Job Satisfaction	0.669	0.000	Sig
	Job Satisfaction -> Job Performance	0.208	0.003	Sig
TOTAL EFFECT	Job Satisfaction -> Employees Participation -> Job Satisfaction	0.877		Sig
DECISION	Partial Mediation			

NB: Sig= Significant

5. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

The paper suggested that job satisfaction has a direct effect on employees' job performance. A critical positive effect of representative commitment on job satisfaction and job performance is that this training is normal or very much rehearsed in the Jordanian Income and Sales Tax Department. Hence, it contributes to a high effect. Employees who are offered opportunities to participate in the decision-making process will, in general, be more satisfied than their job contrasted and employees who are not provided opportunities to partake in decision-making. As indicated by Bhatti and Qureshi (2007), this finding is similar to the current study. Employees concur that designating dynamic at different levels is a necessity where the firm's objective is to accelerate the general client prerequisites/protests/treatment. Yet, DMP expands job satisfaction with the present place of employment while simultaneously unequivocally ensuring EP. Furthermore, specialists accept the conclusions that the organizations are not just helping them with their objectives and consider their own needs. These discoveries negate the discoveries in different settings (Feldman, 1989). Hence, the social exchange arrangements by firms interceding capacity were explained. The relationship of the independent variable and the dependent variable gets more fragile with Baron and Kenny (1986), while the intervening job is ensured. In a similar vein, when the hypothetical model of social exchange is checked within the OST, the greatness of the factors is altered (more grounded), which in the long run creates more significant correspondence. The connection between EP, JS, and JP, as guessed in H1-H4, yields similar number of different analysts found in previous studies, while the intervening connections furnished in H4 are exceptional alongside the directing impact of POS in the general model. This relationship makes this exploration a novel and extended model, an expansion to concentrate from both the perspective of non-financial motivations and the POS. This investigation guarantees researchers to not neglect to check the impact of POS on social exchange and all the more explicitly non-money related parts of the exchange during a discussion. EP is a non-money related and completely adaptable agreement for its employees

from the organizations. This investigation demonstrates the best approach to improve job performance by focusing on the representative's comprehension of authoritative and reminding them for DMP, which does not require any financial advantages. Hence, directors and organizations should focus on these goals to have the most elevated increment in JP while holding themselves in confined or available resources. These discoveries direct administrators that if the organization is not in a situation to give ceaseless compensation financially, it can make a decent blend with DMP to keep the activity at an ideal pace alongside representative satisfaction from their specific positions. Developing individual performance altogether will possibly improve job performance and gain an upper hand than business rivals. Along these lines, by focussing on DMP by JS, all administrators are expected to enhance the yield of by and large firms to accomplish their targets and objectives. Moreover, to expand the quality of the exchange relationship where associations should fuse DMP to build the presentation of job, the view of hierarchical help (on the off chance that it is to be engaged) for the prosperity of its employees will yield and support positive job performance by employees. The sample size for this analysis was taken from the Jordanian Department of Income and Sales Tax. For data collection, simple random sampling technique was used. In this analysis, the measure of perception was measured concerning independent and dependent variables along with the mediator. Data were collected via questionnaire. Future research should gather data using focus group and interviews that can further expand and improve the reach and validity of the findings. In the left-hand variables, more dimensions of non-monetary compensation behaviors can be included in the model to increase the significance of the magnitude that these variables collectively generate when determining dependent variables.

References

- 1) Abdulai, I. A. and Shafiwu, A. B. (2014) 'Participatory decision making and employee productivity. A case study of community banks in the upper east region of Ghana', *Business and Economics Journal*, 5(3), 1.
- 2) Aboyassin, N. A. (2008) 'Managers' belief in employees' job and psychological readiness and employees' participation in decision making: A comparison between American and Jordanian managers', *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 18(3), 252-266.
- 3) Aburayya, A., Alshurideh, M., Alawadhi, D., Alfarsi, A., Taryam, M., & Mubarak, S. (2020). An investigation of the effect of lean six sigma practices on healthcare service quality and patient satisfaction: testing the mediating role of service quality in Dubai primary healthcare sector. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(8), 56-72.
- 4) Advani, A. and Gulzar, S. (2018) 'Impact of employees participation on Job satisfaction evidence from Karachi's tertiary education sector', *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches*, 5(2), 42-51.
- 5) Afshar, H. S. and Doosti, M. (2016) 'Investigating the Impact of Job Satisfaction/Dissatisfaction on Iranian English Teachers' Job Performance', *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 4(1), 97-115.
- 6) Akuoko, K. O., Dwumah, P. and Ansong, F. (2012) 'Employee Involvement in Decision Making and Workers' Performance in Selected Organizations in Ashanti Region of Ghana', *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Management Studies*, 2(6), 11-23.
- 7) Al-Adwan, A. S., Nofal, M., Akram, H., Albelbisi, N. A., & Al-Okaily, M. (2022). Towards a Sustainable Adoption of E-Learning Systems: The Role of Self-Directed Learning. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 21, 245-267.

- 8) Alas, R. (2007) 'The impact of employee participation on job satisfaction during change process', *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 5(4), 28-33.
- 9) Al-Bashayreh, M., Almajali, D., Altamimi, A., Masa'deh, R. E., & Al-Okaily, M. (2022). An Empirical Investigation of Reasons Influencing Student Acceptance and Rejection of Mobile Learning Apps Usage. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 4325.
- 10) Al-Fadl, M. (2004) *Quantitative Methods in Management*, Amman, Jordan:Dar Al Yazuri Publishing and Distribution.
- 11) Al-Hamdan, Z. M., Bawadi, H. A., Redman, R. W. and Al-Nawafleh, A. H. (2016) 'Perception of Jordanian nurses regarding involvement in decision-making', *Applied Nursing Research*, 30, e1-e5.
- 12) Alkhwalidi, A.F., Alobidyeen, B., Abdulmuhsin, A.A. and Al-Okaily, M. (2022). Investigating the antecedents of HRIS adoption in public sector organizations: integration of UTAUT and TTF. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, Vol. and No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-04-2022-3228>.
- 13) Allozi, A., Alshurideh, M., AlHamad, A., & Al Kurdi, B. (2022). Impact of transformational leadership on the job satisfaction with the moderating role of organizational commitment: case of UAE and Jordan manufacturing companies. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 21, 1-13.
- 14) Al-Naimat, S. M. A. (2013) 'Theoretical and analytical study of tax law in Jordan according to the: income tax and sales tax and its relationship with revenues and tax evasion', *International Journal of Financial Research*, 4(3), 107-126.
- 15) Al-Okaily, A., Abd Rahman, M. S., Al-Okaily, M., Ismail, W. N. S. W., & Ali, A. (2020). Measuring success of accounting information system: applying the DeLone and McLean model at the organizational level. *J. Theor. Appl. Inf. Technol.*, 98(14), 2697-2706.
- 16) Al-Okaily, A., Al-Okaily, M., & Teoh, A. P. (2021b). Evaluating ERP systems success: evidence from Jordanian firms in the age of the digital business. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-04-2021-0061>.
- 17) Al-Okaily, M. (2021). Assessing the effectiveness of accounting information systems in the era of COVID-19 pandemic. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-08-2021-0148>.
- 18) Al-Okaily, M., & Al-Okaily, A., (2022). An Empirical Assessment of Enterprise Information Systems Success in a Developing Country: The Jordanian Experience. *The TQM Journal*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-09-2021-0267>.
- 19) Al-Okaily, M., Alghazzawi, R., Alkhwalidi, A.F. and Al-Okaily, A. (2022a). The effect of digital accounting systems on the decision-making quality in the banking industry sector: a mediated-moderated model", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-01-2022-0015>.
- 20) Al-Okaily, M., Alqudah, H., Al-Qudah, A. A., and Alkhwalidi, A.F. (2022b). Examining the Critical Factors of Computer-Assisted Audit Tools and Techniques Adoption in the Post-COVID-19 Period: Internal Auditors Perspective. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-12-2021-0311>.
- 21) Al-Okaily, M., Natour, A. R. A., Shishan, F., Al-Dmour, A., Alghazzawi, R., & Alsharairi, M. (2021a). Sustainable FinTech Innovation Orientation: A Moderated Model. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 1-12.
- 22) Alotaibi, A. A. M. and Al Sharija, M. M. (2016) 'Obstacles Hindering Teachers' Participation in Decision Making in Secondary Schools in the State of Kuwait', *Journal of Educational & Psychological Sciences*, 17(4).

- 23) Al-Qudah, A. A., Hamdan, A., Al-Okaily, M., & Alhaddad, L. (2022). The impact of green lending on credit risk: evidence from UAE's banks. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-18224-5>.
- 24) Al-Saqer, S. (2014) The effectiveness level of procedures at the department of income and sales tax in Jordan from employees' perspectives, unpublished thesis Yarmouk University, Irbid, Jordan.
- 25) Alshurideh, M. (2014). The factors predicting students' satisfaction with universities' healthcare clinics' services. *Dirasat. Administrative Sciences*, 41(2), 451-464.
- 26) Altarawneh, I. (2009) 'Training and Development evaluation in Jordanian Banking Organizations', *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 17(1), 1-23.
- 27) Alwan, M., & Alshurideh, M. (2022). The effect of digital marketing on value creation and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(4), 1557-1566.
- 28) Alzoubi, H. M., & Alshurideh, M., Al Kurdi, B., Inairat, M. (2020). Do perceived service value, quality, price fairness and service recovery shape customer satisfaction and delight? A practical study in the service telecommunication context. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 8(3), 579-588.
- 29) Alzoubi, H. M., Ahmed, G., & Alshurideh, M. (2022a). An empirical investigation into the impact of product quality dimensions on improving the order-winners and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 36(2), 169-186.
- 30) Alzoubi, H., Alshurideh, M., Kurdi, B., Akour, I., & Aziz, R. (2022b). Does BLE technology contribute towards improving marketing strategies, customers' satisfaction and loyalty? The role of open innovation. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(2), 449-460.
- 31) Amah, E. and Ahiauzu, A. (2013) 'Employee involvement and organizational effectiveness', *Journal of Management Development*, 32(7), 661-674.
- 32) Ammari, G., Alkurdi, B., Alshurideh, A., & Alrowwad, A. (2017). Investigating the impact of communication satisfaction on organizational commitment: a practical approach to increase employees' loyalty. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 9(2), 113-133.
- 33) Armstrong, M. and Taylor, S. A. (2014) *Handbook of Human Recourse Management Practice*, 13th ed., London:Kogan Page Publishers.
- 34) Arthur, J. B. (1994) 'Effects of Human Resource Systems on Manufacturing Performance and Turnover', *Academy of Management Journal*, 37(3), 670-687.
- 35) Aryee, S., Chen, Z. X., Sun, L. Y., & Debrah, Y. A. (2007). Antecedents and outcomes of abusive supervision: Test of a trickle-down model. *Journal of applied psychology*, 92(1), 191-201.
- 36) Aws, A. L., Ping, T. A., & Al-Okaily, M. (2021). Towards business intelligence success measurement in an organization: a conceptual study. *Journal of System and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 155-170. doi: 10.33168/JSMS.2021.0210.
- 37) Axelin, A., Outinen, J., Lainema, K., Lehtonen, L. and Franck, L. S. (2018) 'Neonatologists can impede or support parents' participation in decision-making during medical rounds in neonatal intensive care units', *Acta Paediatrica*, 107(12), 2100-2108.
- 38) Bakan, I., Suseno, Y., Pinnington, A. and Money, A. (2004) 'The influence of financial participation and participation in decision-making on employee job attitudes', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(3), 587-616.
- 39) Baron, R. M. and Kenny, D. A. (1986) 'The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations', *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 51(6), 1173.

- 40) Beardwell, J. and Claydon, T. (2007) *Human resource management: A contemporary approach*, Pearson Education.
- 41) Bhatti, K. and Qureshi, T. (2007) 'Impact of employee participation on job satisfaction, employee commitment and employee productivity', *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 3(2), 54-68.
- 42) Bhuiyan, M. A. H. (2010) 'Employee Participation in Decision Making in RMG sector of Bangladesh: Correlation with Motivation and Performance', *Journal of Business and Technology (Dhaka)*, 5(2), 122-132.
- 43) Biggar, S., Javadpour, S., Edworthy, Z., Sheaf, G., Coyne, I. and Malone, H. (2017) 'Interventions for promoting participation in shared decision-making for children and adolescents with cystic fibrosis', *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2017(3), CD012578.
- 44) Bojke, L., Claxton, K. and Bravo Vergel, Y. (2006) *Using expert elicitation to resolve issues of structural uncertainty in decision analytic models*, translated by Boston, PA.
- 45) Brewer, G. A., Selden, S. C. and Facer Ii, R. L. (2000) 'Individual Conceptions of Public Service Motivation', *Public Administration Review*, 60(3), 254-264.
- 46) Broadley, C., Champion, K., Johnson, M. P. and McHattie, L.-S. (2016) *From Participation to Collaboration: Reflections on the Co-Creation of Innovative Business Ideas*, translated by Brighton.
- 47) Brown, A. D. (1998) *Organizational Culture*, 2nd ed., London:Financial Times Management.
- 48) Burns, P. (2016) *Entrepreneurship and small business*, Palgrave Macmillan Limited.
- 49) Chang, G. S.-Y. and Lorenzi, P. (1983) 'The Effects of Participative Versus Assigned Goal Setting on Intrinsic Motivation', *Journal of Management*, 9(1), 55-64.
- 50) Chang, Y. T. and Chao, W. W. (2008) 'A Study of Quaxi and Upward Communication Strategies in Taiwan's Media', *Research in Relational Management*, 6(69-94).
- 51) Chhabra, T. N. (2014) *Principles and Practice of Management*, Delhi:Dhanpat Rai & Co (P) Ltd.
- 52) Chizoba, N., Abomeh, O. S., Chika, O. and Njide, M. (2019) 'Impact of Participatory Decision Making on Organisational Goal Attainment', *International Journal of Business, Economics and Management*, 6(1), 1-15.
- 53) Clark, A. S., Davis, L. A. and Roy, E. J. (1985) 'A possible physiological basis for the dud-stud phenomenon', *Hormones and Behavior*, 19(2), 227-230.
- 54) Coch, L. and French Jr, J. R. P. (1948) 'Overcoming resistance to change', *Human relations*, 1(4), 512-532.
- 55) Cole, G. A. (1997) *Personnel Management: Theory and Practice*, 4th ed., London:Letts Educational.
- 56) Colombo, E. and Stanca, L. (2014) 'The impact of training on productivity: evidence from a panel of Italian firms', *International Journal of Manpower*, 35(8), 1140-1158.
- 57) Cotton, J. L. (1993) *Employee involvement: Methods for improving performance and work attitudes*, Employee involvement: Methods for improving performance and work attitudes., Thousand Oaks, CA, US:Sage Publications, Inc.
- 58) Cox, A., Zagelmeyer, S. and Marchington, M. (2006) 'Embedding employee involvement and participation at work', *Human Resource Management Journal*, 16(3), 250-267.
- 59) Daft, R. L. and Lewin, A. Y. (1993) 'Where Are the Theories for the "New" Organizational Forms? An Editorial Essay', *Organization Science*, 4(4), i-vi.
- 60) Dalal, R. S., Lam, H., Weiss, H. M., Welch, E. R., & Hulin, C. L. (2009). A within-person approach to work behavior and performance: Concurrent and lagged citizenship-counterproductivity associations, and dynamic relationships with affect and overall job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(5),

1051-1066.

- 61) David, F. R. (2011) *Strategic management: Concepts and cases*, Peason/Prentice Hall.
- 62) Deming, W. E. (1982) *Quality, productivity and competitive position*, Cambridge:MIT Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- 63) Deming, W. E. (1986) *Out of the crisis*, Cambridge:Cambridge University Press.
- 64) Den Hartog, D. N. and Verburg, R. M. (2004) 'High performance work systems, organisational culture and firm effectiveness', *Human Resource Management Journal*, 14(1), 55-78.
- 65) Denison, D. R. and Mishra, A. K. (1995) 'Toward a Theory of Organizational Culture and Effectiveness', *Organization Science*, 6(2), 204-223.
- 66) Ding, C. G. and Shen, C.-K. (2017) 'Perceived organizational support, participation in decision making, and perceived insider status for contract workers: A case study', *Management Decision*, 55(2), 413-426.
- 67) DuBrin, A. J. (2015) *Leadership: Research findings, practice, and skills*, Nelson Education.
- 68) Effere, P. M. S., ed. 3rd, pp85. London:Trans-Atlantic Collage. (2005) *Management Styles*, 3rd ed., London:Trans-Atlantic Collage.
- 69) Ehiane, S. O., Adejuwon, K. D., & Goyayi, M. L. J. (2019). Enhancing public sector performance in developmental state in Nigeria: between rhetoric and reality. *AFFRIKA Journal of Politics, Economics and Society*, 9(2), 47-66.
- 70) Einarsen, S., Raknes, B. R. I., & Matthiesen, S. B. (1994). Bullying and harassment at work and their relationships to work environment quality: An exploratory study. *European journal of work and organizational psychology*, 4(4), 381-401.
- 71) Einarsen, S., Skogstad, A., Rørvik, E., Lande, Å. B. & Nielsen, M. B. (2018). Climate for conflict management, exposure to workplace bullying and work engagement: a moderated mediation analysis. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(3), 549-570.
- 72) Fahim, M. M. (1996) *Global Participation in Comparative Law and Egyptian Law*, Egypt:Al-Ma'aref Establishment.
- 73) FarajAllah, A. M. A., El Talla, S. A., Naser, S. S. A. and Al Shobaki, M. J. (2018) 'Participation of Administrative Staff in Decision-Making and Their Relation to the Nature of Work in Universities'.
- 74) Farh, J.-L. and Cheng, B.-S. (2000) 'A Cultural Analysis of Paternalistic Leadership in Chinese Organizations' in Li, J. T., Tsui, A. S. and Weldon, E., eds., *Management and Organizations in the Chinese Context*, London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 84-127.
- 75) Farnham, B. R. (1997) 'A Study of Political Decision Making', [online], available: <https://www.h-net.org/reviews/showpdf.php?id=2002> [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 76) Ferrell, O. C. and Fraedrich, J. (2015) *Business ethics: Ethical decision making & cases*, Nelson Education.
- 77) García Gustavo, A. (2019) 'Employee involvement and job satisfaction: a tale of the millennial generation', *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 41(3), 374-388.
- 78) Groen, B. A., Wouters, M. J., & Wilderom, C. P. (2017). Employee participation, performance metrics, and job performance: A survey study based on self-determination theory. *Management Accounting Research*, 36, 51-66.
- 79) Gündüz, E. (2014) 'Participation to Decision Making: Does Manager Choose Opportunity Rather than Threat?', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, 890-898.
- 80) Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on partial least squares structural*

equation modeling (PLS-SEM). Sage publications.

- 81) Hair, F.H., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2014), A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA
- 82) Han, T.-S., Chiang, H.-H. and Chang, A. (2010) 'Employee participation in decision making, psychological ownership and knowledge sharing: mediating role of organizational commitment in Taiwanese high-tech organizations', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(12), 2218-2233.
- 83) Harbison, F. and Myers, C. A. (1959) *Management in the Industrial World: An International Analysis*, ed. 1st. New York: McGraw-Hill, New York:McGraw-Hill.
- 84) Harris, R. (2012) 'Introduction to Decision Making', [online], available: <https://www.virtualsalt.com/crebook5.htm> [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 85) Hartzell, D. (2006) *Dictionary of Management*, New Delhi:Academic India Puplicher.
- 86) Hassan, A. A. A. (2001) *Business Management and 21st Century Challenges*, Cairo:Dar Kebaa for Printing, Publishing and Distribution.
- 87) Hayajneh, N., Suifan, T., Obeidat, B., Abuhashesh, M., Alshurideh, M., & Masa'deh, R. (2021). The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction through the mediating role of job stress in the Jordanian telecommunication sector. *Management Science Letters*, 11(1), 315-326.
- 88) Heller, F., Pusic, E., Strauss, G. and Wilpert, B. (1998) *Organizational participation: Myth and reality*, Oxford University Press.
- 89) Holland, P., Pyman, A., Cooper, B. K. and Teicher, J. (2011) 'Employee voice and job satisfaction in Australia: The centrality of direct voice', *Human Resource Management*, 50(1), 95-111.
- 90) Irawanto, D. W. (2015) 'Employee participation in decision-making: evidence from a state-owned enterprise in Indonesia', *Management-Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*, 20(1), 159-172.
- 91) ISTD (2017) 'Annual Report', [online], available: [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 92) ISTD (2019) [online], available: <http://www.istd.gov.jo/English/AboutISTD/Profile.aspx> [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 93) Jagero, N., Komba, H. V. and Mlingi, M. N. (2012) 'Relationship Between on the Job Training and Employee's Performance in Courier Companies in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania', *International Journal of Humanities & Social Science.*, 2(22), 114-120.
- 94) Jones, G. R., George, J. M. and Hill, C. W. L. (2000) *Contemporary management*, Irwin/McGraw-Hill.
- 95) Karatepe, O. M. and Olugbade, O. A. (2009) 'The effects of job and personal resources on hotel employees' work engagement', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28(4), 504-512.
- 96) Kemelgor, B. H. (2002) 'A comparative analysis of corporate entrepreneurial orientation between selected firms in the Netherlands and the USA', *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 14(1), 67-87.
- 97) Khan, M., Mdyusoff, R., Hussain, A. and Ismail, F. (2019) 'The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship of HR Practices and Employee Job Performance. Empirical Evidence from Higher Education Sector', 8(2019), 78-94.
- 98) Konings, J. and Vanormelingen, S. (2014) 'The Impact of Training on Productivity and Wages: Firm-Level Evidence', *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 97(2), 485-497.
- 99) Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C. M., Hildebrandt, V. H., De Vet, H. C. W. and Van der Beek, A. J. (2014) 'Construct validity of the individual work performance questionnaire', *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 56(3), 331-337.

- 100) Kulbashian, S., Appelbaum, S. H., Makarenko, D., Louis, D., Saluja, J. and Meleshko, O. (2013) 'Participation in decision making: a case study of job satisfaction and commitment (part one)', *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 45(4), 222-229.
- 101) Kurdi, B., Alshurideh, M., & Alnaser, A. (2020). The impact of employee satisfaction on customer satisfaction: Theoretical and empirical underpinning. *Management Science Letters*, 10(15), 3561-3570.
- 102) Lahsen, M. (2016) 'Trust through participation? Problems of knowledge in climate decision making' in *The social construction of climate change*, Routledge, 197-220.
- 103) Likert, R. (1967) *The human organization: its management and values*, The human organization: its management and values., New York, NY, US: McGraw-Hill.
- 104) Locke, E. A. and Schweiger, D. M. (1979) 'Participation in decision-making: One more look', *Research in organizational behavior*, 1(10), 265-339.
- 105) Malkawi, B. H. and Haloush, H. A. (2008) 'The case of income tax evasion in Jordan: symptoms and solutions', *Journal of Financial Crime*, 15(3), 282-294.
- 106) Mancilla García, M. and Bodin, Ö. (2019) 'Participation in Multiple Decision Making Water Governance Forums in Brazil Enhances Actors' Perceived Level of Influence', *Policy Studies Journal*, 47(1), 27-51.
- 107) Markey, R. (2006) 'The internationalisation of representative employee participation and its impact in the Asia Pacific', *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 44(3), 342-363.
- 108) Matteson, M. T. and Ivancevich, J. M. (1999) *Management and Organization Behavior Classics*, Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill.
- 109) Mayfield, M. and Mayfield, J. (2015) 'The Effects of Leader Motivating Language Use on Employee Decision Making', *International Journal of Business Communication*, 53(4), 465-484.
- 110) McGuire, R. (2005) 'Which Management Style to Use ', *The Pharmaceutical Journal*, 275(9), 317-320.
- 111) Meleshko, O., Makarenko, D., Saluja, J., Kulbashian, S., Louis, D. and H. Appelbaum, S. (2013) 'Participation in decision making: a case study of job satisfaction and commitment (part two)', *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 45(6), 352-358.
- 112) Miller, K. I. and Monge, P. R. (1986a) 'Participation, Satisfaction, and Productivity: A Meta-Analytic Review', *The Academy of Management Journal*, 29(4), 727-753.
- 113) Miller, K. I. and Monge, P. R. (1986b) 'Participation, Satisfaction, and Productivity: A Meta-Analytic Review', *Academy of Management Journal*, 29(4), 727-753.
- 114) Mohsan, F., Nawaz, M. M., Khan, M. S., Shaukat, Z. and Aslam, N. (2011) 'Are employee motivation, commitment and job involvement inter-related: Evidence from banking sector of Pakistan', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(17), 226-233.
- 115) Moorhead, G. and Griffin, R. W. (2008) *Organizational behavior managing people and organizations*, Dreamtech Press.
- 116) Morin, L., & Renaud, S. (2004). Participation in corporate university training: its effect on individual job performance. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences/Revue Canadienne des Sciences de l'Administration*, 21(4), 295-306.
- 117) Muindi, F. K. (2011) 'The Relationship Between Participation in Decision Making and Job Satisfaction among Academic Staff in the School of Business, University of Nairobi', *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2011(2011), 1-34.
- 118) Munizu, M. (2013) 'Total Quality Management (TQM) Practices toward Product Quality Performance: Case at Food and Beverage Industry in Makassar, Indonesia', *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-*

- JBM), 9(2), 55-61.
- 119) Nafei, W. (2015). The effects of job embeddedness on organizational cynicism and employee performance: A study on Sadat City University. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 6(1), 8-25.
 - 120) Needle, D. (2004) *Business in Context: An introduction to business and its environments*, 4th ed., London:Thomson Learning.
 - 121) Noah, Y. (2008) 'A Study of Worker Participation in Management Decision Making Within Selected Establishments in Lagos, Nigeria', *Journal of Social Sciences*, 17(1), 31-39.
 - 122) Noe, R. A. (1986) 'Trainees' Attributes and Attitudes: Neglected Influences on Training Effectiveness', *Academy of Management Review*, 11(4), 736-749.
 - 123) Odumeru, J. A., & Ogbonna, I. G. (2013). Transformational vs. transactional leadership theories: Evidence in literature. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 2(2), 355-361.
 - 124) Ohemeng, F. L., Amoako-Asiedu, E., & Darko, T. O. (2018). The relationship between leadership style and employee performance. *International Journal of Public Leadership*.
 - 125) Ojokuku, R. M. and Sajuyigbe, A. S. (2014) 'Effect of Employee Participation in Decision Making On Performance of Selected Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos, Nigeria', *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(10), 93-97.
 - 126) Okon, F. I. and Isong, E. U. (2016) 'Management Styles and Employees' Performance in Small Scale Business Enterprises in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria', *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 4(1), 51-61.
 - 127) Ölçer, F. and Florescu, M. (2015) 'Mediating effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between psychological empowerment and job performance', *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 22(3), 111-136.
 - 128) Oyebamiji, F. F. (2018) 'Influence of Employees Participation in Decision Making on Organization Performance: A Study of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho, Oyo State, Nigeria'.
 - 129) Pashiardis, P. (1994) 'Teacher Participation in Decision Making', *International Journal of Educational Management*, 8(5), 14-17.
 - 130) Pathak, R. C. G. J. o. F. S. M. D. V., Iss. 3/4, (2005): 59-69. (2005) 'Flexibility - Thinking Shift for Organizational Excellence', *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 6(3/7), 59-69.
 - 131) Pearce, J. A. and Robinson, R. B. (1989) *Management International Edition*, Singapore:McGraw-Hill.
 - 132) Peng, Y. P. (2014). Job satisfaction and job performance of university librarians: A disaggregated examination. *Library & Information Science Research*, 36(1), 74-82.
 - 133) Pisano, P., Pironi, M. and Rieple, A. (2015) 'Identify Innovative Business Models: Can Innovative Business Models Enable Players to React to Ongoing or Unpredictable Trends?', *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 5(3), 181.
 - 134) Preuss, G. and Lautsch, B. (2002) 'The Effect of Formal Versus Informal Job Security on Employee Involvement Programs', *Relations industrielles*, 57(3), 517-541.
 - 135) Rahmat, R., Ramly, M., Mallongi, S., & Kalla, R. (2019). The leadership style effect on job satisfaction and performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management and Education*, 2(1).
 - 136) Ramzy, O., El Bedawy, R., & Maher, A. (2018). Dysfunctional Behavior at the Workplace and Its Impact on Employees; Job Performance. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 9(4), 224-233.
 - 137) Rastegar, A., Seif, M. H., Ardekani, Z. F. & Tajvaran, M. (2019). The Relationship of Transformational

- Leadership Style with Bullying at Work with Regard to the Mediating Role of Organizational Health among Employees of Shiraz University of Medical Sciences. *Journal of Payavard Salamat*, 13(4), 0-0.
- 138) Ravasi, D. and Schultz, M. (2006) 'Responding to Organizational Identity Threats: Exploring the Role of Organizational Culture', *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(3), 433-458.
- 139) Reynolds, J. (2004) *Helping People Learn: Strategies for Moving from Training to Learning*, London:CIPD.
- 140) Riaz, A., & Haider, M. H. (2010). Role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 1(1), 29-38.
- 141) Robert, F. (2018). Impact of Workplace Bullying on Job Performance and Job Stress. *Journal of Management Info*, 5(3), 12-15.
- 142) Romiszowski, A. J. (2016) *Designing instructional systems: Decision making in course planning and curriculum design*, Routledge.
- 143) Rusteberg, R., Rahman, M. A., Sadah, M. A., Rabi, A. and Sauter, M. (2010) 'Water management strategies analysis using multiple criteria decision techniques towards sustainable development of northern Gaza strip', *Proceedings of BALWOIS*.
- 144) Sashkin, M. (1976) 'Changing toward participative management approaches: A model and methods', *Academy of Management Review*, 1(3).
- 145) Sepulveda, F. (2005) 'Training and Productivity: Evidence for US Manufacturing Industries', Available at SSRN 830406.
- 146) Shadur, M. A., Kienzle, R. and Rodwell, J. J. (1999) 'The Relationship between Organizational Climate and Employee Perceptions of Involvement: The Importance of Support', *Group & Organization Management*, 24(4), 479-503.
- 147) Shaed, M. M., Ishak, S. and Ramli, Z. (2015) 'Employees' participation in decision making (PDM): A literature survey', *Malaysian Journal of Society and Space*, 11(13), 142-155.
- 148) Shami, L. and Nino, M. (2001) *Administration: Basic Principles*, 1st ed., Amman, Jordan:National Center for Publishing.
- 149) Snyder, G. H. and Diesing, P. (2015) *Conflict among nations: Bargaining, decision making, and system structure in international crises*, Princeton University Press..
- 150) Spagnoli, P., & Balducci, C. (2017). *Do high workload and job insecurity predict workplace bullying after organizational change?* *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, 10(1), 2–12.
- 151) Spreitzer, G. M. and Mishra, A. K. (1999) 'Giving Up Control without Losing Control: Trust and its Substitutes' Effects on Managers' Involving Employees in Decision Making', *Group & Organization Management*, 24(2), 155-187.
- 152) Spreitzer, G. M., Kizilos, M. A. and Nason, S. W. (1997) 'A dimensional analysis of the relationship between psychological empowerment and effectiveness, satisfaction, and strain', *Journal of Management*, 23(5), 679-704.
- 153) Sproedt, A., Plehn, J., Schönsleben, P. and Herrmann, C. (2015) 'A simulation-based decision support for eco-efficiency improvements in production systems', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 105, 389-405.
- 154) Stashevsky, S. and Elizur, D. (2000) 'The effect of quality management and participation in decision-making on individual performance', *Journal of Quality Management*, 5(1), 53-65.
- 155) Stohl, C. and Cheney, G. (2001) 'Participatory processes/paradoxical practices: Communication and the dilemmas of organizational democracy', *Management Communication Quarterly*, 14(3), 349-407.

- 156) Stone, D. L. and Eddy, E. R. (1996) 'Model of individual and organizational factors affecting quality-related outcomes', *Journal of Quality Management*, 1(1), 21-48.
- 157) Stoner, J. A., Freeman, R. E. and Gilbert, D. A. (1995) *Management*, 6th ed., New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- 158) Survey Monkey (2019) 'Sample size calculator', [online], available: https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/lp/sample-size-calculator/?utm_expId=.cOMQLyUQhqbVct5bsJIAA.1&utm_referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 159) Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics* (6. bs.). ISO 690
- 160) Talley, J. L. (2011) 'Decision Making in Organizations', [online], available: <http://www.jltalley.com/presentations/Decision%20Making.pdf> 16 February 2018].
- 161) Tannenbaum, R. and Schmidt, W. H. (1973) How to choose a leadership pattern, *Harvard Business Review* Boston, MA.
- 162) The Economic Policy Council (2017) 'Jordan Economic Growth Plan 2018-2022', [online], available: <http://www.ssif.gov.jo/UploadFiles/JEGProgramEnglish.pdf> [Accessed 1 May 2019].
- 163) Thiagarajan, P., Chakrabarty, S., & Taylor, R. D. (2006). *A Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Reilly's Role Overload Scale. Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66(4), 657-666.
- 164) Thompson, G., Buch, R. and Kuvaas, B. (2017) 'Political skill, participation in decision-making and organizational commitment', *Personnel Review*, 46(4), 740-749.
- 165) Timming, A. R. (2015) 'The 'reach' of employee participation in decision-making: exploring the Aristotelian roots of workplace democracy', *Human Resource Management Journal*, 25(3), 382-396.
- 166) Ting, K. S. (2012) The level and effects of participation in decision making (PDM) on employee groups for the manufacturing and servicing sectors in Malaysia, unpublished thesis Universiti Tunku Abdul Rahman.
- 167) Tourani, A. and Rast, S. (2012) Effect of employees' communication and participation on employees' job satisfaction: An empirical study on airline companies in Iran, translated by Singapore.
- 168) Townsend, A. (2016). Understanding and addressing bullying in the workplace. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 40(5), 270-273.
- 169) Uzun, T. and Ozdem, G. (2017) 'The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship between Teachers' Perceptions of Supervisor Support and Job Performances', *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 9(7), 84-90.
- 170) Vandenabeele, W. (2009) 'The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Self-Reported Performance: More Robust Evidence of the PSM-Performance Relationship', *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 75.
- 171) Vertsberger, D. and Gati, I. (2016) 'Career decision-making difficulties and help-seeking among Israeli young adults', *Journal of Career Development*, 43(2), 145-159.
- 172) Vroom, V. H. (1964) *Work and motivation*, Wiley New York.
- 173) Wagner Iii, J. A. (1994) 'Participation's effects on performance and satisfaction: A reconsideration of research evidence', *Academy of Management Review*, 19(2), 312-330.
- 174) Wagner Iii, J. A., Leana, C. R., Locke, E. A. and Schweiger, D. M. (1997) 'Cognitive and motivational frameworks in US research on participation: a meta-analysis of primary effects', *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 18(1), 49-65.

- 175) Westwood, R. and Chang, A. (2002) *Headship and Leadership. Organizational Behavior: Southeast Asian Perspectives*, 3rd ed., Hong Kong:Longman.
- 176) Williamson, M. G. (2008) 'The Effects of Expanding Employee Decision Making on Contributions to Firm Value in an Informal Reward Environment*', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 25(4), 1183-1209.
- 177) Wong, K. (2010) 'Handling small survey sample size and skewed dataset with partial least square path modeling,' *Vue: The Magazine of the Marketing Research and Intelligence Association*, November, pp.20–23
- 178) Xu, Y.-p., Shi, F.-l., Yang, F. and Zhu, Y.-f. (2010) 'Requirement analysis method in naval battleships design based on QFD and operational simulation techniques [J]', *Systems Engineering-Theory & Practice*, 1.
- 179) Yada, H., Lu, X., Omori, H., Abe, H., Matsuo, H., Ishida, Y., & Katoh, T. (2015). *Exploratory Study of Factors Influencing Job-Related Stress in Japanese Psychiatric Nurses. Nursing Research and Practice, 2015, 1–7.*
- 180) Yehuda, B. and Brooks, C. H. (2008) 'Survey response rate levels and trends in organizational research', *Human Relations*, 61(8), 1139-1160.
- 181) Yoerger, M., Crowe, J. and Allen, J. A. (2015) 'Participate or else!: The effect of participation in decision-making in meetings on employee engagement', *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 67(1), 65.
- 182) Zaqout, I., Abu-Naser, S. S., El Talla, S. A. and Al Shobaki, M. J. (2018) 'Information Technology used and it's Impact on the Participation of Administrative Staff in Decision-Making in Palestinian Universities'.
- 183) Zellman, E., Kaye-Blake, W. and Abell, W. (2010) 'Identifying consumer decision-making strategies using alternative methods', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 13(3), 271-286.
- 184) Zhu, Y., Xie, Y., Warner, M. and Guo, Y. (2015) 'Employee participation and the influence on job satisfaction of the 'new generation' of Chinese employees', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 26(19), 2395-2411.